

Ferric nitrate promoted synthesis of 6-carbomethoxy-1,2-pyrone from veratrole

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6-Carbomethoxy-1,2-pyrone has been obtained in the cation-radical catalysed chain oxygenation of veratrole promoted by ferric nitrate in methanol. The formation of this product has been rationalised.

Perumal and Barker¹ studied the cation-radical catalysed chain (CRCC) oxygenation of ketenimines in the presence of ferric nitrate in methanol. This paper reports the aromatic ring cleavage of veratrole and the formation of the lactone, viz. 6-carbomethoxy-1,2-pyrone (**1**) using the above mentioned catalyst. Liang and Foote² reported the dicyanoanthracene (DCA) sensitised photooxygenation of veratrole. However, a different product was obtained applying Fe^{3+} ions promoted thermal condition. This provides a simple method to get 6-carbomethoxy-1,2-pyrone, which is otherwise difficult to synthesise.

Results and Discussion

The pyrones are used as substrates for palladium-catalysed [4+3]cycloadditions³. The principal strategies⁴ developed for α -pyrones synthesis includes γ -acylation of an ester dienolate, reaction of a ketone enolate with a 2-carbalkoxyvinyl cation equivalent and reaction of an ester enolate anion with a 2-acylvinyl cation equivalent.

Alkyl-substituted pyrones have also been prepared by the reaction of enamines with two equivalents of ketene⁵. Exploiting the conjugate addition of methyl 2-lithio-2-(phenylthio)acetate to α,β -enones⁶ and transition-metal reagents⁷, α -pyrones could be obtained. Vinylogous thiol esters and α -oxoketenedithioacetals have also been successfully converted into α -pyrones⁸.

Avoiding the reported tedious and multistep synthesis, this note elaborates the synthesis in a much simpler way by CRCC oxygenation of veratrole using ferric nitrate in methanol. During these reactions controlled experiments with benzoquinone as a super oxide quencher showed that the oxygenation did take place. This suggests that the oxygenating species is molecular oxygen and a plausible mechanism for the formation of this lactone is delineated in Scheme 1.

It may be suggested that the charge transfer (CT) complexation between Fe^{3+} and veratrole lowers the ionisation potential of veratrole so that the species-A can accept an

electron from the complex to propagate the chain⁹. Fe^{3+} compounds, with low negative electrode potential, forms a CT complex which requires oxygen to break up the CT complex through the electron transfer from the complex to oxygen.

Experimental

Veratrole (Aldrich) was used. M.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes. Ir and ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on Bruker FTIR-IFS85 and Bruker (200 MHz) instruments respectively.

Typical procedure : A mixture of veratrole (3.76 g, 20 mmol), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 g, 5 mmol) in methanol (30 ml) was heated on a steam-bath for 3 h. It was then poured in

cold water and extracted with methylene chloride (3 × 30 ml). The combined organic layers was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The crude product on chromatography afforded 6-carbomethoxy-1,2-pyrone as the major product (3 g, 50%), m.p. 72° (lit.¹⁰ 74°), ν_{\max} (KBr) 1730 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.31 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz) and 6.40–6.64 (2H, m). Hydrolysis of this product gave the corresponding acid¹¹ (m.p. 127–28°).

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